

Enhanced Scenario Generation for Integrated-Power and Telecommunication Infrastructures Using the RESTART Sampling Technique

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Abstract

The growing interest in using multi-fidelity Grey-Box Models (GBMs) for real-time monitoring and risk assessment of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) [1–3] is due to their ability to jointly exploit physical knowledge and data mining to lower models complexity while keeping accuracy and interpretability [4–6]. Still, the GBM use is limited because its training is challenged by the combinatorial number of normal and accidental scenarios that arise because of the dynamic continuous and discrete nature of CPSs [7, 8]. The fidelity of a GBM is indeed related with its ability to catch significant system behaviors when exposed to harm or hazards. This can only be achieved via advanced exploration techniques capable of identifying (maybe) rare scenarios that would otherwise be overlooked by standard crude Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) [9, 10]. In this work, we explore the use of Repetitive Simulation Trials After Reaching Thresholds (RESTART) proposed in [9, 11], that is an advanced splitting-based importance sampling technique to effectively train the GBM of a CPS. The RESTART method is used for probing the space of event sequences, adaptively and intelligently allocating the simulation efforts preferably on those sequences leading to outcomes of interest for the objective of training the GBM to simulate normal and accidental scenarios. Our case study consists of an Integrated-Power and Telecommunication (IP&TLC) infrastructure, in which several failure modes leading to a vast number of accidental scenarios are to be considered.

Index Terms—Cyber-physical systems, grey-box models, scenario generation, importance sampling

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